

A Psycho- Analytical Reassessment in Anita Desai's Cry, the Peacock and in Bharati Mukherjee's Wife: A Comparative Study

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Karuthappandi, T. "A Psycho- Analytical Reassessment in Anita Desai's Cry, the Peacock and in Bharati Mukherjee's Wife: A Comparative Study." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 6–10.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2588176>

T. Karuthappandi

Head – Department of English

Pachamuthu College of Arts & Science for Women, Dharmapuri

The term 'Comparative Literature' is difficult to define for it evolves not one but two or even more than two literatures in comparison at the same time. It becomes still more difficult task when the comparatist has to take into consideration the multi-dimensional aspects of comparative literature such as-linguistic, cultural, religious, economic, social and historical factors of different societies.

Indian women novelists venture woman as the central figure by giving a divergent dimension to their image in the family and society. Their insight into the woman's reactions and responses, problems and perplexities and the complex working of their inner selves and their emotional association and disturbances enabled these novelists to succeed in presenting the predicament of women most effectively. The existential struggle to establish one's identity, to assert one's individuality, fight to exist as a separate identity, cultural conflicts, the social and economic changes, the problem of the expatriates and immigrants and the personal relationships especially between man and wife are some of the common themes that appear in the novels of Indian women novelists. We find the fullest expression of women problems through display of various themes in the novels of Anita Desai and Bharati Mukherjee. Anita Desai's protagonist Maya in *Cry, the Peacock* gives expression to the long smothered wail of hurt psyche. Maya's tale is a tale of blunted human relationships. With heightened imagination, sensitivity, loneliness and lack of healthy communication with her husband she becomes complex, confused, irrational and a neurotic individual. Bharati Mukherjee's Dimple in *Wife* lacks a stable sense of personal and cultural identity and is a victim of fantasies and other forms of social oppression.

The great Indian and Indian expatriate novelists like Anita Desai, Shashi Deshpande, Nayantara Sahgal and R.P. Jhabvala and Bharati Mukherjee have won world wide recognition in exploring the suppressed selves of Indian women through different female characters and are regarded as champion of femininity in Indian

context. Maya of Anita Desai's novel *Cry, the Peacock* (1980) and Dimple of Bharati Mukherjee's novel *Wife* (1990) act and behave abnormally, after their marriage, in different relations and situations even with their own husbands. Both the novelists have tried to concentrate at the fact that they are not born abnormal but assume abnormality with the crippling effect of social relation, cultural morality and ethical values on the one hand and failure of fulfillment of their fantasy on the other. The conflict in the life of Maya results because of temperamental differences but it shouldn't be looked upon as social and domestic discard but it is deeply rooted in the fantasy of childhood experience and the prophecy of albino astrologer regarding death of one of the partners four years after marriage and it gets aggravated at the death of a pet dog to.

Both Desai's Maya and Mukherjee's Dimple experience psychic disturbances due to severe demands on their personality. We come across despair, frustration, loneliness and fear in Dimple and the psychological states give way to hallucination, thoughts of death that culminate in madness and violence. But Maya's retreat to her past does not save her from her problems. Both the past and present become equally unacceptable and dissatisfying and Maya resorts to the last refuge for a neurotic, suicide or homicide.

Mukherjee's *Wife* is a cluster of corroding images suggestive of the deteriorating mind of Dimple. She employs images of corrosion, decomposition, disease and death skillfully. Desai skillfully correlates the landscape of the novels to the psychic states of the sensitive individuals that people her canvass. The city of Delhi highlights the lack of affinity experienced by Maya. The parties, dances, drinks and gossips in the club disturb her inner mind considerably. The cry of the peacock forms the background music suggesting her sexual starvation. The deteriorating psychic conditions and different moods of Maya are portrayed by using highly functional images. Imminent death is reminded to her as the tension in her aberrant mind accelerates the disturbing images of slimy crawling creatures: "Albinos, Bleached into albinos by the desert sun, these lizards. But the rat, too, is an albino, from having lived always in the dark, from never having seen the sun at all" (127). Besides the memory of the prophecy associated incidents too augment her trouble. Her brother Arjuna's letter confirms that the astrologer, the horoscope and the tantrums are not figments of an insane nightmare and curious hallucination but facts. This makes her fear-stricken by which she associates even the ordinary events and remarks with the prediction of the albino astrologer. The culminating tension leads to severe headaches which are symptomatic of the desire to elude the issue. But reality can no longer be eluded and fears and thoughts crowd her mind. Maya fails to visualize any strategy to achieve tranquility. Nightmares intensify her suffering and gradually descend her into the abyss of darkness and aloneness where the only echoes are those of the albino and the peacock. Even the deteriorating psychic condition of Dimple is portrayed through hallucinations which give way to thoughts of suicide. She has nightmares of violence, of suicide and of death. She even has the sensation of being raped and killed in her flat. To her, death appears to present itself in myriad forms. Sleepers look to her more like corpses than as people under temporary suspension of consciousness. Her friend in a Mullick appears in her dream as dead who properly interpreted could mean that Dimple fervently wishes herself dead. It is her nightmarish visions and dreams that highlight her latent impulses which gradually deteriorate her to a state of neurosis.

Dimple of *Wife* on the other hand dreams of freedom and love, which marriage might confer upon but she is ambiguous regarding love and freedom, as she could not visualize the fact that freedom and love also have certain limitations and find her dreams and aspirations shattered and unfulfilled. Both Maya and Dimple fail to grasp the real vision of life and are led to neurosis and become morbid due to vast gap between fantasy and reality. The present paper concentrates at the causes of morbidity and the ways how to come out of the mess to make the life blissful and of worth living.

There lies great similarity in the deeds performed by the heroines of both the novels *Cry, the Peacock* and *Wife*. In both the novels heroines go the extreme of killing their husbands. Maya of *Cry, the peacock* is born in post Independent India but her up-bringing is undertaken very much in accordance to the culture and morality of Pre-independent India where female child is considered to be the esteem of the dynasty, a typical but one of the most rigid of middle class moralities, and even the slightest deviation from the set ethical values may damage heavily the grace of dynasty and so are given utmost care accompanied with a lot of restrictions and superstitions. Maya is married to Gautama, a man of academic pursuits and contrary to her romantic and fanciful nature, it was almost a marriage of contradictory temperament hand-picked by her parents. Now Maya becomes victim of two fold conflicts, social and matrimonial on the one hand and on the other internal conflict rooted in the childhood memory and fantasy over shadowed with the prophesy of an albino astrologer regarding the death of either of the partners four years after marriage. Death of the pet dog to aggravates her fear of death and becomes the prominent concerns of her consciousness. Now obsessed with the feelings of death she develops brooding attitude and turns to be introvert and neurotic. Maya's unhappiness can be traced in part to external circumstances, her over protected childhood and adolescence which makes it difficult for her to face the realities of adult life, Oedipus complex for excessive love and dependence on her father which makes her seek his substitute in her husband and obviously could not succeed. Anita Desai explores the tormented consciousness of Maya with stream of consciousness technique evoking both, the positive and negative images.

All her moments of present are closely attached with her memory of the past and she appears to be eternally entrapped with her past. Maya's agony and despairs aroused out of unfulfilled emotional relationship of married life is expressed through several symbolic associations like frenzied dance of the peacock for its mate, the call for love and mating given by the "pigeons etc. Maya's fascination for "Pigeon's nests that were filled with babies", (*Cry, the Peacock* p.35) is suggestive of her longings for motherhood. Her unfulfilled marital relationship has transformed her feelings of fascination into fatal call of separation in the bird's love making and mating. Consequently we discover her fanciful world transformed into chaos under the severe impact of prophecy of impending death and the resultant anguish. Dimple, the protagonist of *Wife* has very immature view about marriage which she thinks bring out freedom and love, completely unaware of the concept of freedom and love and because of her ambiguous attitude she always feels incomplete and "She thought of Premarital life as a dress rehearsal for actual living"² (*Wife*, P.3). She finally gets married to Amit, after painful waiting a middle class, un imaginative, young engineer who dreams of making fortune in America and after retirement to live a comfortably rich life in Calcutta, India. Soon after her marriage Dimple feels cheated because her adolescent mind cannot grasp that freedom too has certain limitations. She finds a very big gap between the world of her fancy and reality that she faces in the real world. She behaves resentfully with her in-laws and resents her husband for she finds him unable to fulfill the fantasy she has nourished from childhood, so aggravates her depression. At this stage when she reconstructs the image of ideal man from faces from magazines, she finds herself unable to identify with anyone in the family and gets frantically enraged at the prospects of becoming mother.

One of the most blessed moment of life to complete the meaning of womanhood appears to her an outrage on body and wishes to dispose of the "tyrannical and vile" thing deposited in her body, through abortion. In such an overwhelming situation she decides to start afresh in America leaving behind all the sources of her depression and despair and to live an exciting and fanciful life. But once again she finds her aspirations frustrated for Amit collapses inwardly because of the temporary joblessness in America and shuns the life of fancy and luxury once again, earlier she has

met disappointment because of the marriage against her dream of marrying a neurosurgeon and to relish the luxuries of consumerist society. Infact “Dimple’s problem is her utter rootness”³ and she could not succeed in adapting with either of the cultures, inherited or acquired and appears to be on the cross-roads of life with utmost perturbation. Another shocking situation that Dimple discovers is that America with all its glitter allows Indian wives only to create little India but doesn’t allow either freedom or fulfillment as evident in the case of Ina Mullick who, despite her desperate attempts at becoming a total American remains a frustrated individual. After such disturbing realization Dimple feels isolated inwardly so much that she finds herself unable to welcome the new prospect after Amit gets a job. She makes certain pathetic attempts to get merged into the new culture through practicing the trick of flirting with Americans but discovers complete estrangement from herself and her surrounding as well. Now she is discovered to be caught into a very conflicting situation where her mind is conditioned by the commercials on T.V. and magazines so much that she is unable to distinguish it from the world of reality. Dimple is now emotionally caught into two world, Indian culture questions her outrageous adultery but her present self aspire to become American by any means and just to suppress her guilty conscious on the one hand and on the other to feel American like characters of T.V. Serials kills Amit her own husband. The best aspect of the novel lies in “the tension and balance between the personal and the social”⁴ but certainly not in estrangement from society and dissociation not from reality rather real reality of life. To conclude we discover that both the characters Maya and Dimple are living a life justified by the metaphorical implications of their names, like illusion and depression and always find themselves away from the elixir of life, a life of love and consummation. What they need utmost is to enlarge their outlook and vision of life that life is more a matter of adjustment; than achievement and through this moderate attitude they ought to have exerted for the fulfillment of their aspirations but it could not be denied that people is society should also rise higher from petty gender distinction and to some extent equal opportunity and freedom to female child should also be given.

There are differences between these writers in their novelistic techniques, approaches, themes and in their use of language. Nevertheless this study reveals that there is certain common pattern running through both the novels. The general pattern seems to be that of the protagonist as victim of the patriarchal order who fights against various forces in order to resolve the issues in her own ways. The search of their protagonists is mainly for love, understanding, recognition and identity. The existential struggle to establish one’s own identity, to assert one’s individuality and fight to exist as a separate identity elucidates that feminism has commonly echoed in both the novels by these feminist writers. They have shown that Maya and Dimple fail to establish good interpersonal relationships due to uncongenial domestic environments characterized by emotional deprivation, lack of understanding, parental neglect or pampering and lack of peer group or sibling support. Broken marital relations, sexual abuse, loneliness, despair, identity crisis, thwarting of individuality, dislocation and culture shock to contribute to darken the lives of these women. The stories of such Maya and Dimple can be made successful in a world where nobody is inferior or superior, where men and women are equally valued, where they become complementary to each other, where silence is broken, where positive recognition and learning to assimilate without surrendering individuality is gained.

References

1. Desai, Anita, *Cry the, peacock*, London; chatto and windus. 1973
2. Mukherjee, Bharti, *Wife*, Penguin Books, 1990.
3. Jain, Jasbir, “Forgiveness of spirit: The world of Bharati Mukherjee’s Novels”, *The Journal of Indian writing in English*, Vol.13, July 1985, No. 2, PP. 12-19

4. Williams, Raymond, "Realism and the contemporary Novel", *Twentieth Century Literary Criticism*, ed. David Lodge (London : Longman,1972), PP. 590-
5. Prasad Madhusudan. *Anita Desai, the Novelist*, Allahabad: New Horizon, 1981.
6. Rao B. Ramachandra: *The Novels of Ms. Anita Desai: A Study*, Ludhinana: Kalyani, 1977.
7. Meena, Belliappa. *Anita Desai- A Study of her Fiction*. Calcutta: Writer's Workshop, 1971.
8. Sudhir Kakar, *Feminine Identity in India Women in Indian Society: A Reader*, ed. Rehana Ghandially (New Delhi: Sage, 1988).